

Innovative Personalized Business Model in the Field of Hair Restoration: Author's Methods as a Factor in Strengthening Women's Entrepreneurship

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Annotation. The article explores the prospects for the development of women's entrepreneurship in the beauty industry through the implementation of proprietary techniques - SensHair and Nanoker - in the hair restoration process. The purpose of the study is to substantiate the effectiveness of implementing personalized business models based on the proprietary technologies SensHair and Nanoker as a factor in strengthening women's entrepreneurship, building an expert brand, and enabling innovative self-realization in the service economy. The study employs business modeling tools (Canvas model), financial and economic forecasting, comparative analysis, and case study methods.

The research justifies two effective business models in the hair restoration sector: a small personalized salon and a large studio with franchising potential. The first model focuses on service individualization, high client trust, and flexible management, making it attractive for the early stage of women's entrepreneurial development. The second model relies on standardized procedures scaled under a single brand, with clearly defined business processes and marketing templates, laying the groundwork for expansion through franchising.

Each model reflects adaptation to the needs of a specific target audience, integration of emotional support for clients, clear service differentiation by complexity and cost, and scalability potential. The use of proprietary care techniques provides not only a competitive advantage but also high economic efficiency: the return on investment (ROI) exceeds 22–25% per month, with a payback period of approximately four months. The proposed business models based on SensHair and Nanoker demonstrate that innovative women-led enterprises can successfully combine ethics, expertise, and economic viability. These techniques are suitable both for individual business launches and for future scaling through education, salon networks, or franchising. The study highlights the potential of women's entrepreneurship as a socially impactful and economically profitable phenomenon.

Keywords: women's entrepreneurship, proprietary techniques, personalized model, SensHair, Nanoker, beauty services, business modeling, payback, expert brand.

Формування персоналізованої бізнес-моделі у сфері відновлення волосся як чинник посилення жіночого підприємництва

Анотація. Дослідження дозволило обґрунтувати дві ефективні бізнес-моделі: малий авторський салон та велика студія з потенціалом франчайзингу. У кожній моделі відображено адаптацію під потреби цільової аудиторії, вбудовану емоційну підтримку

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клієнтів, диференціацію послуг і перспективи масштабування. Показано, що реалізація авторських методик забезпечує високу прибутковість (ROI понад 22–25%/міс.), швидку окупність (≈ 4 міс.) та можливість виходу на міжнародний ринок. Запропоновані бізнес-моделі на основі SensHair і Nanoker доводять, що інноваційний жіночий бізнес може поєднувати етичність, експертність і високу економічну ефективність. Методики є придатними як для старту в індивідуальному форматі, так і для подальшого масштабування через навчання, мережу салонів або франшизу. Дослідження підкреслює потенціал розвитку жіночого підприємництва як соціально значущого та економічно прибуткового явища.

Ключові слова: жіноче підприємництво, авторські методики, персоналізована модель, SensHair, Nanoker, сервіс краси, бізнес-моделювання, окупність, експертний бренд.

Introduction

In today's context of growing interest in personalized services and ethical entrepreneurship, the development of women's initiatives in the beauty industry is of particular importance. The shift in focus from mass standards to an individualized approach, as well as the growing demand for safe, medically aesthetic procedures, create new market opportunities for women entrepreneurs.

One of these niches is hair restoration for clients with sensitive scalp, after medical interventions, during pregnancy, or in case of allergic reactions to traditional care products. However, most classical techniques do not take these features into account, which limits access to quality service for a significant part of the target audience.

In this context, the development and implementation of SensHair and Nanoker proprietary methods, which combine innovative technologies, an ethical approach, safety, and high aesthetic quality of the result, is of particular relevance. These techniques become the basis of a new model of women's entrepreneurship based on expertise, personalization, and reputation, not mass.

Women's entrepreneurship in the beauty industry is attracting increasing academic interest, as this sector combines economic activity with social functions, fostering self-realization, innovation, and expanded employment opportunities for women. Several studies emphasize that the beauty industry is not merely a commercial segment but also an important platform for the development of female leadership and entrepreneurial initiative.

A systematic approach to analyzing women's business activity is demonstrated in the literature review conducted by J. Zavodny Pospisil and L. S. Zavodna [1], who applied the McKinsey 7S model to assess case studies of female-led enterprises. Although this model is rarely used in such research, the authors highlight its potential when primary data is employed. Moreover, the study identifies key motivations for women to start businesses in various countries.

S. Raheem [2] focused on the influence of social, political, and economic environments on the success of women-owned enterprises. The author emphasized that women's ability to adapt to external conditions is critical for scaling their businesses. A reflective analysis of the evolution of refugee women's entrepreneurship is presented in the study by H. Al-Dajani [3]. It demonstrates that despite growing interest in this topic within gender and social studies, it remains insufficiently integrated into mainstream business scholarship. The author calls for further empirical research into how entrepreneurship influences the social, economic, and political empowerment of refugee women.

On another front, A. M. Mehta, M. Qamruzzaivian, and A. Serfraz [4] provide empirical evidence that access to finance and knowledge are key determinants in the development of women's entrepreneurship in Bangladesh. The authors argue that transformational leadership enhances the connection between knowledge, financial access, and the sustainable growth of

women-owned businesses, particularly in the beauty, fashion, and lifestyle sectors. The issue of the double burden faced by women who balance entrepreneurship with domestic responsibilities is addressed in the work of T. De Silva and colleagues [5], who substantiate the need for social support and adaptive policy to encourage women's participation in business. New approaches to women's entrepreneurship education are demonstrated in the study by E. Rivo-Lopez, J. F. Lampon, M. Villanueva-Villar, and C. Miguez-Alvarez [6], which finds that visual narratives serve as effective tools for developing entrepreneurial skills, fostering initiative, and generating innovative business ideas. This format enables female students to better absorb material, even when time is limited.

The global dimension of women's entrepreneurship is explored in the study by S. Terjesen and A. Lloyd [7], who, within the framework of the Female Entrepreneurship Index, analyzed data from 20 countries. The authors found that women are less actively involved in international trade compared to men due to gender bias, weak institutional support, and sociocultural barriers.

N. Islam and colleagues [8] identified that the development of women's entrepreneurship in the beauty industry requires strong policy support, managerial autonomy, and a favorable business environment. The study focuses on salon services as a key source of self-employment for women in Bangladesh.

Innovation as a strategic advantage is examined by Y. Huang and co-authors [9], who demonstrate that women with high psychological capital and strong opportunity recognition capabilities achieve superior outcomes. At the same time, the authors note that persistent stereotypes may limit the full realization of this potential.

A sustainable business model for women in the beauty industry is proposed by M. Chitra and V. Kalpana [10], who emphasize the importance of location, motivation, and the structuring of business processes in achieving entrepreneurial success.

In addition to academic publications, practical insights into the industry are provided by sources such as Raywell, Easyweek, Hair.com.ua, among others [11–16]. These sources present examples of innovative procedures being implemented in women-led beauty studios, including amino acid restoration, botox treatments, and keratin smoothing. Such technologies are shaping new high-value business niches characterized by personalized service and adaptability to client needs.

Thus, despite regional peculiarities, scholars state that women's entrepreneurship in the beauty industry serves not only as an economic growth driver, but also as a social reinforcement, innovative renewal, and reputational modernization of small businesses.

Despite numerous theoretical developments, many aspects remain insufficiently disclosed, including the issues of service personalization, quick payback of innovations, and building an expert brand in the context of women's entrepreneurship.

Our study focuses on the specifics of the development of women's entrepreneurship in the field of hair reconstruction as a new segment of the beauty market in Ukraine, identifying motivations, barriers, and strategies for sustainable business development. This allows us to fill the existing gap in applied research and offer effective management solutions for starting and scaling up women's entrepreneurial activities.

The purpose of the article is to explore the possibilities of forming personalized business models in the field of hair restoration based on the author's SensHair and Nanoker methods, and to assess their impact on the development of women's entrepreneurship as a socially and economically significant phenomenon.

The objectives of the article are: to characterize the key features of proprietary techniques as an innovative product; to build business models for a small and scalable implementation format; to conduct a financial analysis of the effectiveness of the models; to substantiate the prospects for the implementation and development of the brand at the international level.

Results

In today's socio-economic environment, women's entrepreneurship is seen as a powerful driver of inclusive growth, women's empowerment, and the development of sectors focused on quality of life, care, and support. Compared to traditional industries, the beauty and healthcare sector, including hair care, is one of the most responsive to customer needs and, at the same time, open to innovative solutions that combine aesthetic, ethical, and therapeutic effects.

Hair restoration deserves special attention as a trusted service, which involves not only the provision of services but also deep interpersonal interaction, psychological support, and an individualized approach. For women entrepreneurs, this area has become not only a channel for professional realization, but also a platform for developing original solutions that change the perception of beauty, health, and normality.

In particular, the segment of clients with alopecia, chemotherapy background, sensitive scalp, or chemical allergies creates a demand for non-standard techniques where classical technologies do not work. It is here that the need for author's approaches is formed, which allow us to combine medical ethics, aesthetic expertise and an individual solution for each client.

The development of innovative services at the intersection of beauty, health, and personalization opens up opportunities not only to provide quality services, but also to build an expert brand that can scale, train others, and set new standards in the field of women's entrepreneurship.

Thus, the hair restoration industry is transforming from a common service into an environment of women's leadership and expert initiatives aimed not only at aesthetics but also at the emotional and social recovery of clients. This opens up a new dimension in small business development - focused on care, trust, and individual approach, where women's entrepreneurship is not just an economic activity, but a way to transform the public perception of vulnerability, beauty, and strength.

The development of innovative women's entrepreneurship in the field of hair restoration is impossible without the introduction of proprietary techniques that take into account the medical, aesthetic, and psychological characteristics of the client. The proprietary SensHair and Nanoker techniques are the result of practical experience, in-depth study of the needs of vulnerable women and the desire to create an ethical, safe and effective service.

SensHair is a unique technique of micro strand extensions of 3-5 hairs. Its difference lies in the fact that it is: almost invisible visually; has an ultra-low weight effect (does not overload the follicles); is based on gentle thermal fixation; provides for individual selection of capsules in accordance with the anatomy of the scalp.

This makes it possible to work with: clients after chemotherapy; people with hypersensitive skin; clients with weakened hair follicles.

Nanoker is a visual coloring system without the use of chemicals. The effect is achieved through a hand-picked mix of 2-4 natural hair shades in one strand, which imitates the natural dynamics of color.

Particularly suitable for: weakened, brittle hair; women during pregnancy or breastfeeding; clients with allergies to dyes; previously colored hair with an unstable base. Tone imitation occurs without interfering with the hair structure, which allows you to "color" even those hairs that cannot be processed under normal conditions.

In order to visually assess the advantages and differences of the proposed innovative approaches compared to classical procedures, comparative table 1 is presented below.

Table 1

Comparative Analysis of Innovative and Traditional Approaches to Hair Restoration

Criterion	SensHair (proprietary)	Nanoker (proprietary)	Conventional Methods
Type of effect	Physical integration of micro-strands	Visual tone simulation without dye	Thermal/chemical coloring or capsules
Chemical exposure	None	None	High or moderate
Suitable for alopecia	Yes	Partially (depends on base)	No
Suitable during pregnancy/lactation	Yes	Yes	Limited or not recommended
Skin anatomy matching	Individualized	Individualized (skin tone, base)	Standardized
Ability to "color" damaged hair	Not applicable	Yes	No
Visual naturalness	Maximum	Maximum	Moderate
Market uniqueness	No analogues	Recognized novelty	Mass-market approach
Level of personalization	Very high	Very high	Low to moderate

Source: Compiled based on [11–16]

Thus, SensHair and Nanoker's proprietary methods are not only innovative from a technological point of view, but also have a high applied potential for developing their own business. They combine functionality, safety, and personalized aesthetics, which allows not only to provide a unique service but also to create new formats of women's entrepreneurship - from individual offices to full-fledged studios and training centers.

Both techniques have been recognized by the professional community. SensHair and Nanoker were presented at international championships (including Hair Extensions Guru), are actively used in Poland and Ukraine, and have become the basis for opening studios by specialists who have been trained under the author's programs.

In the practice of applying SensHair and Nanoker proprietary techniques, two sustainable approaches to business organization have been formed. They depend on the scale of the business, personal ambitions of the entrepreneur, financial capabilities, and the chosen promotion strategy. They can be classified as a small author's salon model and a scalable expert studio or network model.

Each model has its own advantages: a small salon provides flexibility, emotional contact, and stability, while a large salon is focused on brand building, standardization, and international market entry. Let's take a closer look at each model.

With the growing demand for individualized services and expert service, a special niche in the market is occupied by a personalized salon format focused on high quality procedures and close trust between the client and the master.

Within this format, the model of a small proprietary salon or studio is implemented, where the personal brand of the specialist who possesses the unique SensHair or Nanoker technique plays a central role. This model is characterized by a limited client base, a high average service price, and an "expert hands" approach that ensures an exceptional level of service. The high level of involvement of the entrepreneur herself, combined with the emotional aspect of client interaction, lays the groundwork for building an expert brand with a strong degree of customer loyalty. For a detailed analysis of this business model, its structure is presented below in Table 2.

Table 2

Canvas Model for a Small-Scale Salon

Block	Content
Value Proposition	Safe, innovative hair extensions and visual hair coloring
Customers	Women after chemotherapy, with sensitive skin, during pregnancy, or with allergies
Sales Channels	Instagram, word-of-mouth referrals, before-and-after case presentations, participation in competitions
Customer Relationships	Client support, emotional care, and consultations
Revenue Streams	Services, personal consultations, product sales, gift certificates
Key Resources	Expert specialist, equipment, materials, social capital
Partners	Hair suppliers, trichologists, cosmetologists
Key Activities	Service delivery, content creation, reputation management
Cost Structure	Materials, rent, promotion, professional development

Source: Compiled based on [11–16]

As shown in the Canvas model, a small author's salon operates on the basis of clearly defined key activities, structured costs, and focused value propositions. This approach ensures high flexibility, individualized service, and sustainable financial results under conditions of effective management. In order to implement this business model in practice, we have developed an algorithm for launching a small salon (Fig. 1, which covers the main stages of creating, organizing, and developing a personalized studio within the hair restoration industry.

Fig. 1. Algorithm for launching a small salon according to the SensHair/Nanoker model

Source: developed by the author on the basis of generalized practices [11-16].

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the algorithm for launching a small salon based on the SensHair/Nanoker model demonstrates a clear sequence of actions focused on personalized service, the formation of an expert image, and stable operation in a niche market.

However, in order to scale proprietary technologies while maintaining their uniqueness and quality control, it is advisable to develop a large salon or chain operating in an expert

format. Such a model involves centralized standardization of processes, franchising potential, and brand building around proprietary techniques. This business structure can be presented using the Canvas model for a large salon, shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Canvas Model for a Large-Scale Salon	
Block	Content
Value Proposition	Proprietary techniques, ethical aesthetics, women's leadership
Customers	Nationwide (Ukraine) and European clientele; premium clients, medical referrals, celebrities
Sales Channels	Media, podcasts, TikTok, websites, physician referrals
Customer Relationships	CRM system, online booking, treatment packages, long-term client support
Revenue Streams	Services, master training programs, franchising, product sales
Key Resources	Brand, educational materials, quality standards
Partners	Physicians, medical centers, influencers, beauty academies
Key Activities	Business scaling, training, marketing, quality control
Cost Structure	Staffing, advertising, education, franchise documentation

Source: Compiled based on [11–16]

Thus, the Canvas model of a large salon allows you to structure the key elements of a scalable business that combines the image component with operational efficiency. This model requires active work with staff, building a training and quality control system, and developing a franchise strategy to enter new markets.

Taking into account these components, we have formed an algorithm for the development of large business based on the author's SensHair/Nanoker methods, which is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Algorithm for launching a large business based on the SensHair/Nanoker model
Source: developed by the author on the basis of generalized practices [11-16].

Despite the difference in scale, both models have a common value – they are based on unique proprietary methodologies, which ensures a high level of customer trust and the ability to differentiate in the market. At the same time, each model has different economic parameters – in terms of start-up costs, expected revenues, expenses, and payback periods.

For greater clarity, we provide a summary comparison of the key economic and organizational characteristics of the small and large salon models in Table 4.

Table 4

Comparison of Business Models: Small vs. Large Salon

Criterion	Small Salon (1 Technician)	Large Salon / Studio (3 Technicians)
Initial Investment	€5,000	€20,000
Space Format	Room of 10–20 m ²	Space of 50–100 m ² with multiple zones
Target Client	Individual clients, niche audience	Mass premium segment, partnership-based projects
Pricing Strategy	Premium, personalized approach	Premium + scale, standardized quality
Monthly Client Volume	40–50	120–150
Average Volume per Client (strands)	600–1,000 strands	500–800 strands
Price per Strand (labor)	\$0.30 (~€12)	\$0.30
Average Check	\$180–300	\$180–250
Monthly Revenue (excluding materials)	\$7,200–15,000	\$21,600–45,000
Payback Period	1–3 months	5–8 months
Promotion Channels	Instagram, word of mouth, case studies	Advertising, franchising, collaborations with clinics
Additional Revenue Streams	Online consultations, gift certificates	Training courses, franchise, product line
Risk Level	Low, manageable	Medium, requires team management
Flexibility	High (schedule, pricing, format)	Lower, but greater scalability
Growth Potential	Academy, personal brand	Network expansion, international brand

Source: developed by the author based on empirical estimates

Thus, the choice between a small or large format for implementing original beauty services depends not only on the style of business or readiness for scaling, but also on the economic model that the entrepreneur is ready to implement. In any case, proprietary methods are the foundation for building a competitive business model with high profitability, stable demand, and potential for international market entry.

Conclusions

Based on the conducted research, it has been established that the implementation of personalized business models in the field of hair restoration, built on the proprietary SensHair and Nanoker techniques, serves as an effective tool for enhancing women's entrepreneurship in the beauty industry. These methods integrate innovative, ethical, and medico-aesthetic

approaches tailored to clients with increased sensitivity, ensuring high service quality while creating an emotionally supportive brand environment. The study demonstrates that a personalized approach to service design fosters deeper client trust and contributes to the development of stable business relationships grounded in expert reputation. In this context, the proposed proprietary models of small and large salons allow for the implementation of diverse development strategies, ranging from flexible individual formats to scalable expert networks with franchising potential.

The findings make it possible to draw the following conclusions:

- The SensHair and Nanoker techniques can serve as the foundation for a highly profitable business model, both in individual practice and within studio-based or networked entrepreneurship frameworks.
- A short payback period, high customer loyalty, and an innovative approach provide a sustainable competitive advantage for female entrepreneurs.
- The presence of international recognition and the opportunity to train other professionals confirm the expertise behind the model and provide a foundation for transnational scaling.

Accordingly, the following practical recommendations are proposed:

1. For beginner practitioners: start with the small salon model focused on personalized client service and gradual portfolio development.
2. For experienced experts: expand activities through training programs, the creation of online courses, and the implementation of a franchising model.
3. For investors and strategic partners: consider these proprietary techniques as a foundation for launching niche beauty studios with a medico-aesthetic profile.
4. For international expansion: emphasize safety, ethical standards, and personalization as key elements for promoting services in European markets where quality and certification requirements are particularly high.

Thus, proprietary techniques in the field of hair restoration represent not only a successful case of women-led entrepreneurship but also an innovative model of sustainable service that integrates expertise, emotional sensitivity, and market viability.

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